

THE POLITICAL SITUATION OF THE FIRST QUARTER OF THE 20TH CENTURY IN KASHADARYO OASIS

Poyonov.T

Free researcher of Karshi state uiversity

Abstract: In this article, the political situation in the Kashkadarya region in the first quarter of the 20th century is considered based on archival sources, and the opinions about the life of the villages are summarized.

Key words: uezd, volost, election, village, council, bureau, party committee, soviet apparatus, station, party members.

Most of the peasants were previously influenced by the printing press and their supporters (emir officials, rich people, clan chiefs) due to their influence and had a negative attitude towards the Soviet power. [3:1492- 1495] cannot be ignored, of course. This movement was severely disrupted during the campaign to end printing. The military crackdown paved the way for great successes in the strengthening of punitive measures, the elimination of printers and their assistants, the propaganda conducted among the population in this area gave positive results, and the peasant masses encouraged the Soviet authorities.

The rich stood firm to prevent such changes in the population [4:135-138], handed over some people who sided with the Soviet government to the oppressors, intensified terror. This increased the hatred of the peasants towards the rich and the printers. Just as a strict military crackdown was put in place against the rich, and they were required to quickly hand over their oppressors (i.e. [5:1-6], the oppressors from the same clan), the populace itself began to actively fight against the oppressors, began to accuse the rich of helping the printers, because of which the rich were in a difficult situation and had to give receipts for the delivery of their own printers.

In addition to these, at the request of the population, to the gangs of printers a volunteer who engages in mass armed struggle against formation of detachments at the expense of the rich was also carried out. This is a severe disruption of the printing industry in the region opened the way for it to be [1:40].

At the end of December 1925, according to the Kashkadarya regional party committee, there were 214 faction members and 140 candidates, a total of 354 communists. Most of the party members and candidates were sent to the region, the military was recruited from other places [6:96-100], and there were very few representatives of the local population who joined the party. Almost all of the 8 people

who became members of the party were women. In this case, the Bolsheviks in Kashkadarya were not expected to reach the level of political power that represented the will of the people, and the Soviet power was held by the army and penal authorities during this period[7:121-123]. The position of the committee of the executive power in relation to the party was significant. This is probably why, in the report under review, it is recognized that "the Red Army party organization in the territory of Kashkadarya region, according to its political height, is extremely high compared to the branches of the REGIONAL party organization" [2:44]. The fact that branches or party cells did not take root in the life of the region and did not have influence is also reflected in the bottom numbers. On January 1, 1925, there were 6 sect cells in Behbudi city and Karshi station. There were 4 cells in Shahrisabz district and city. Volosts, 2 in Beshkent, a total of 28 cells, 2 of which are in these regions, 1 of them in other one in the village, 2 in Koson, in the villages. There were 9 cells under volost executive committees and volost factional committees, and the remaining 22 were in cities.

It is natural to ask the question [8:128-131] what was the level of Soviet construction during this period. The report also reflects on this. We will quote them:

Until October 1925, there was almost no real sub-Soviet apparatus in the villages and volosts. During the reign of the Republic of Bukhara, the inhabitants of the villages and some districts of the region did not see any real representative of the Soviet power[9:128-132]. Until October 1925, not a single village council was formed among tens of thousands of rural residents, except in the centers of the volosts. Volosts had no prestige[10:223-226], had no influence on the masses, revkoms were just revolutionary committees.

Most of the population was under the influence of emir officials, rich people and clan chiefs. Moreover, the existence of the printing press made it difficult and hindered the establishment of real Soviet power. For this reason, the problem of transferring the anti-printing company to the party organizations and the regional executive committee [11:186-190] on the one hand, and building a real Soviet apparatus in the villages on the other hand, was seen as a cross-cutting issue.

In order to carry out this campaign, at the meeting of the executive bureau of the regional party committee on September 8, 1925, 3 commissions were formed, one for each of the three uezds. In addition to these commissions and those in charge of uezds [12:59-63].

After that, the comrades included in the commission prepared for the work and its implementation, drew up plans, the work done in the Executive Bureau of the region

on October 3, 1925 was discussed [13:686-692] and the planned plan for the organization of Soviet bodies in the volosts and villages was accepted.

In Bekhbudi uezd, the Soviet commission visited 36 villages and held 55 rallies and 42 interviews[14:386-391]. About 10,000 Dekhkons took part in these gatherings, and in return, elections to the Soviets were carried out. As a result, the structure of village and volost soviets was renewed by 95%, the old okokols were not brought closer to the soviets. 4 volost executive committees and 10 village councils were formed in Guzor uezd.

As for Shahrisabz uezd, all the attention of the commission was directed to the end of printing, and the election campaign was not held for village and volost soviets.

Indeed, the number of participants in electoral activities and meetings was not up to the required level [15:292-296], according to the constitution, this situation is explained by the fact that the suppression movement and its non-termination until now prevented a large part of the male population from participating in the elections" [16:64]

During the years 1920-1925, the Soviet authorities could not make any progress in the economic, social and cultural life of Kashkadarya region[17:342-346]. Bringing the people to the brink of starvation is expressed by the brutality of the Bolsheviks in their management, their selective violence, and the fact that the state path is recklessly far from the democratic, people-friendly principles.

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